

A STUDY OF THE SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC OBSTACLES OF MUSLIM GIRL'S EDUCATION IN ALLAHABAD DISTRICT, UTTAR PRADESH

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Abstract:

Present study is an attempt to examine the Social and Economic Obstacles of Muslim Girl's Education in Allahabad District, Uttar Pradesh. The tool consists of self prepared questionnaire having 15 questions. Questions were asked to Muslim Girls, their Parents, Hindu and Muslim Teachers respectively. Education for Muslim Girls has joined a wider recognition all over the world. Today in the 21st century we cannot ignore the importance of education for Muslim girls. Quality education is essential for *Muslim* communities in India. According to *Sacchar Committee report* Muslim girls are very poor in comparison of other caste girls and Muslim are lacking in quality education, 25% Muslim children has not seen school, only 4% Muslims are graduate, only one out of twenty Muslims are post graduate, and condition of Muslim girls is much worse. The report also mentions that the Muslims comprise an important category of the deprived communities. In education the performance of Muslim girls has been worst than all social religious Communities. The standard of Islamic Education is not satisfactory as religious education is not properly imparted. Findings of the study reveal that social and economic condition, *Parda Partha*, Religious obstacles and illiteracy among the parents are major hindrances for the Muslim Girls Education.

Key Words: Society, School, Girls Education & Poverty

Introduction:

Muslims constitute India's largest minority as well as the second largest Muslim population in the world after Indonesia. After Indonesia, India has the second largest Muslim population in the world. More than half of the entire Muslim population lives in Bihar, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal. To remove backwardness of the country, to control population rise, child care, to become independent, to avoid exploitation of women, education is necessary. Many committees and commissions were constituted for improving the educational condition of women like the University Education Commission (1948-49), the Secondary Education Commission (1952-53), the National Committee on Women's Education (1958- 59), the Kothari Commission (1964-66), Rama Murti Committee (1990) and National Policy Education, 1986.

The realization of the country's aspirations involves changes in the knowledge, skills and values of the people as a whole. Education for all has gained a wider role and responsibility all over the world. Today in the 21st century we cannot afford to ignore the importance of education for Muslim girl's any longer. Unfortunately this importance has been neglected for centuries. It assumes all the more importance or the 3rd world countries, where colonialism has remained a great force hindering education for the general masses and for the girls of the minority community in particular.

The great Philosopher and Educationist Dr. Radhakrishnan said that there cannot be educated people without educated women. Educationally, Muslims constitute one of the most backward communities in the country causing concern. Muslim girls and women lag behind their male counterparts and women of all other communities (Jabeen, Firdous, 2008).

"Women in India have made momentous efforts during the six decades since independence entering every field of education, and taking on the challenge of different professions and fields. However, large population of women still remain confined by the family anticipations, religious hurdles and social obstacles. Women from different socio-economic level have a great deal of inequality in their life. There are also differences in women's specific prestige across caste, religions and communities" (Usha Nayar, 2007).

The data clearly indicates that while the overall levels of education in India, measured through various indicators, is still below universally acceptable standards, the educational status of the Muslim community in particular is a matter of great concern (Sachar Committee Report).

Islamic Perspectives Involved

ISLAM gives high consideration to education and knowledge. Men and women enjoy the equal rights in this field and uniformly encouraged to seek it with respect to their interest levels. The recitals in the Holy Koran

thoroughly put forward the basic necessities of woman prophets with no bar in being assigned to it. But the education in narrowed down to strict *Islamic* studies only which can be ascertained as one of the major reasons for the backwardness of women in the field of higher education is the prevalent *parda pratha* establishing the above statement. For instance the state of Punjab where the *parda pratha* is dominant, the on roll of Muslim girls in educational institutions is very less.

The sole objective of the present study is to find out the need of Muslims girls education in India with respect to the minority.

Review of the Related Literature:

Nayar, Usha (2007) studied the socio economic condition of Muslim Women and Girls in India. The main objective of the study was to investigate the condition of Education of Muslim Women and Girls in India. Findings of the study show that Muslims are more urbanized than Hindus and Sikh. In 2001, the case of females who married below the legal age of marriage, was highest among Muslims (43.2%) followed by Hindus (37%).The findings further show that Muslims are comparatively educationally backward minority community as compared to other communities in India.

Firdous, Jabeen (2008) investigated the development of education of Muslim Women in Uttar Pradesh since Independence. According to her study Muslims are educationally behind than other communities and Muslim Parents were quite clear that primary education is enough for their daughters.

Khan & Butool (2013) observed that more than half of the total Muslim Indian Population i.e., 53.95 per cent is illiterate with 17.48 per cent literate people just for the name sake only. Apart from it, 21.18 per cent people have completed their primary education only, whereas, the percent share of secondary literates among the Muslims is only 7.44 per cent.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objective of the present study is to investigate the present status of women education in general and the minority women education in particular in India.

In the course of establishment of the above objective, following are the facets that researcher faced while examining it-

- ✓ Social Hindrance
- ✓ Religious Hindrance
- ✓ Economic Hindrance

The brief description is given as under-

- ✓ **Social Hindrance:** It covers the various dominant social aberrations covering the rites; rituals; ceremonies and fundas widespread.
- ✓ **Religious Hindrance:** It covers the various dominant religious aberrations like the fatwa's (statements pronounced by Muslim religious gurus) rules and regulations, hadith (teachings and preachings of the Prophets) and shariah (guidelines of the Holy Koran).
- ✓ **Economic Hindrance:** It covers the affluence factor where the Muslim girls are not economically sound enough to support their education.

Methodology:

Present Research is a Descriptive Survey in nature. The sample of the study consists 100 students randomly selected from various Muslim Girls Colleges of Allahabad District, Uttar Pradesh. The tool consists of self prepared questionnaire having 15 questions. Questions were asked to Muslim Girls, their Parents, Hindu and Muslim Teachers respectively. The data was analysed and thereby interpreted by the average percentage method and graphical representation.

Analysis and Interpretation of the Data:

Statement 1:

There is no separate school for girls and parents do not allow to go to school

Table1: Parents do not allow Girls to go School (Opinion of the Girls)

Girl's Scale	Class X th	Class XII th	Undergraduate	Average Percentage
Agree	88%	100%	48%	78.6%
Indifferent	1%	0%	8%	4.0%
Disagree	8%	0%	44%	17.3%

Figure 1

Table 1 and figure 1 indicate that 88% girls of Xth class, 100% girls of XIIth class 48% undergraduate girls are agreed that parents do not allow going school. Total 78.6% Muslim Girls are agreed that parents do not support for going to school.

Statement 2:

Due to Illiteracy among Muslim Families, they do not understand the Value of Education.

Table 2: Parents do not understand the Value of Education (Opinion of the Girls)

Girls Scale	Class X th	Class XII th	Undergraduate	Average Percentage
Agree	68%	88%	52%	69.60%
Indifferent	00%	4%	14%	6.00%
Disagree	32%	8%	34%	24.60%

Figure 2

Table 2 and fig 2 depict that average 69.60% Muslim Girls students are agreed that parents do not understand the Value of Education.

Statement 3:

Due to *Parda Pratha* in Islam most of the girls do not get the education

Table 3: Most of the Muslim Girls are out of School due to *Parda Pratha* (Opinion of the Girls)

Girls Scale	Class X th	Class XII th	Undergraduate	Average Percentage
Agree	68%	100%	60%	76%
Indifferent	16%	0%	6%	11%
Disagree	16%	0%	34%	25%

Figure 3

Table 3 and fig 3 reveal that 76% Muslim Girls are agreed that most of the Muslim Girls are out of School due to *Parada Pratha*. 76% Muslim girls studying in Xth, XIIth and undergraduate classes accepted that *Parada Pratha* is a big obstacle for the schooling of Muslim girls.

Statement 4:

Due to poor economical condition Muslim guardians do not sent girls to school.

Table 4: Muslim Girls are out of School due to Poor Economical Condition (Opinion of the Girls)

Girl's Scale	Class X th	Class XII th	Undergraduate	Average Percentage
Agree	88%	100%	62%	83.3%
Indifferent	1%	0%	28%	14.5%
Disagree	8%	0%	10%	6%

Figure 4

Table and fig 4 demonstrate that 83.30% Muslim girls are agreed that poor economical condition of the Muslim families is a big reason behind the low enrolment of Muslim girls in the school.

Statement 5:

In comparison to other religion, Muslim girl's percentage in the schools is very low.

Table 5: Muslim Girl's Percentage in the Schools is Very Low (Opinion of the Teachers)

Teacher's Scale	Hindu Teacher	Muslim Teacher	Average Percentage
Agree	68%	88%	78%
Indifferent	1%	0%	1%
Disagree	28%	12%	6%

Figure 5

Table and fig 5 show that 68% Hindu Teacher and 88% Muslim Teachers are agreed that Muslim Girls percentage is very low in the schools.

Statement 6:

Due to Islamic religious "Parda Pratha" Muslim girls are not able to get education.

Table 6: Due to Islamic religious "Parda Pratha" Muslim girls are not able to get education (Opinion of the Teachers)

Teacher Scale	Hindu Teacher	Muslim Teacher	Average
Agree	82%	90%	86%
Indifferent	10%	0%	10%
Disagree	8%	10%	9%

Figure 6

Table and fig 6 show that 82% Hindu Teacher and 90% Muslim Teachers are agreed that Muslim girls are not able to get education due to Parda Partha.

Statement 7:

Majority of Muslim guardians feel that there is no need of Education.

Table 7: Majority of Muslim guardians feel that there is no need of Education (Opinion of Muslim Guardians)

Muslim Guardians Scale	Muslim Guardians
Agree	30%
Indifferent	4%
Disagree	66%

Figure 7

Table and fig 7 demonstrate that 66% guardians are disagreed that there no need of education and 34% guardians accepted that education is not necessary.

Statement 8:

Poor Economical condition is a big reason behind Drop out of the Girls.

Table 8: Poor Economical condition is a big reason behind Drop out of the Girls (Opinion of Muslim Guardians)

Muslim Guardians Scale	Muslim Guardians
Agree	72%
Indifferent	4%
Disagree	24%

Figure 8

It is clear from table and fig 8 that 72% Muslim Guardians said that Poor Economical condition is a big reason behind Drop out of the Girls.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ Total 78.6% Muslim Girls are agreed that parents do not support for going to school.
- ✓ 69.60% Muslim Girls students are agreed that parents do not understand the Value of Education.
- ✓ 76% Muslim girls studying in Xth XIIth and undergraduate classes accepted that *Parda Pratha* is a big obstacle for the schooling of Muslim girls.
- ✓ 83.30% Muslim girls are agreed that poor economical condition of the Muslim families is a big reason behind the low enrolment of Muslim girls in the school.
- ✓ 68% Hindu Teacher and 88% Muslim Teachers are agreed that Muslim Girls percentage is very low in the schools.
- ✓ 82% Hindu Teacher and 90% Muslim Teachers are agreed that Muslim girls are not able to get education due to *Parda Partha*.

- ✓ 66% guardians are disagreed that there no need of education and 34% guardians accepted that education is not necessary.
- ✓ 72% Muslim Guardians accepted that Poor Economical condition is a big reason behind Drop out of the Girls.

Conclusion:

It became apparent that large population of the Muslim girls lack higher education. Thus from the above findings it can be understand that lack of education among the parents, economic backwardness, educational backwardness among parents, absence of co-educational institutions, child marriages are the major challenges enforcing the execution of stern action in fighting against them leading to their eradication. Muslim girls are the least educated section of Indian society. According to the All India Survey of Higher Education (2014-15) Muslims are far behind than scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. Muslims comprise 14% of India's population but only 4.4% of students enrolled in higher education.

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